
e-Business Consumers Perception Level and Trends of Udaipur District

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Abstract E-Business is deemed as the sale and purchase of goods and services through the internet in exchange for money and data transfer to complete the transactions. E-Business is at the forefront of transforming marketing strategies, based on new technologies, and facilitates product information and improved decision-making. In this way, marketing strategy increasingly requires large amounts of information to better understand client needs, which raises the question of choosing the right marketing strategy to better fit consumer expectations. This paper review aims to shed light on both the recent changes of trends in e-Business and its interplay with consumer consumer's perception level. Extant research has examined this change in human perception due to social network building, mostly through the themes of online marketing and social media marketing, also comprehending issues such as cost efficiency, information quality, and trust development towards online shopping. This paper aims to identify research trends in the field through Systematic research on marketing strategy for e-Business. The following findings are presented: Amidst the current competitive global business environment, companies tend to respond with strategies for e-Business and online businesses that resort to e-Business platforms and social networking to better understand consumer needs, and facilitate consumer marketing strategies and share innovative information.

Keywords consumer; perception level

1. Introduction

The digitalization of information and non-information products, due to technological Developments and internet growth, has caused companies to rethink their marketing strategies. Competition has increased due to the creation of an internet-enabled marketplace that competes with the physical marketplace. Consequently, companies have integrated the electronic market in their strategies to increase visibility and access the global market, leading to the growth of E-Business. E-Business refers to the sale and purchase of goods and services through the internet, with the transfer of money and data to complete the transactions-Business platforms facilitate product information discovery that enables comparisons and decision-making. They aim to replicate consumer in-store experiences and interactions to influence purchasing decisions.

Therefore, interactive marketing is significant in the internet-enabled market environment. Consumer marketing strategies, in this case, involve improved engagement and provision of information resources to build knowledge and understand individual needs. Given the rapid increase in and sharing of information in online environments, companies struggle with identifying the most effective engagement and marketing strategies that align with consumer expectations and knowledge levels.

Review of literature

R. Sihare Shyam 2020 "Roles of E-content for E-business: Analysis tract" E-content marketing is an emerging strategy in a marketing arena to shift the paradigm from traditional marketing to digital marketing. Digital

marketing is an appropriate alternative to collaborate with a traditional marketing for enhance marketing strategies to reach globally.

Li Feng 2020 "The digital transformation of business models in the creative industries: A holistic framework and emerging trends" This paper examines how digital technologies facilitate business model innovations in the creative industries. Through a systematic literature review, a holistic business model framework is developed, which is then used to analyze the empirical evidence from the creative industries. the creative industries. Three new themes for future research are highlighted.

Fua Hanliang, Manogaran Gunasekarab, Ming Caoc, Song Jianga, Yangd Aimin 2020 "Intelligent decision-making of shopping behavior based on internet of things" The development of big data and Internet of things (IoT) have brought big changes to e-commerce

Top e-business in Udaipur district: -

Here is a list of top E-Commerce Businesses of Udaipur, not particularly in an order, who have taken over Internet like a storm and made a mark

Lokalart.com- This business venture has its roots from the Lok Kala Art or the folk art and provides an exposure to the local artisans who create ethereal, traditional art forms.

oZopping.com- Ojal Suthar and Millin Panwar opened this business with a different segment of shopping-Grocery! With over multiple outlets of GoZopping.com across India, this venture offers grocery items ranging from home needs, personal needs, beverages, spices, baby products and much more. They deliver items of popular brands at your doorstep and now stands as one of the top e-commerce businesses of Udaipur.

NimishaVerma.com- Having worked previously with Fab India, Nimisha Verma opened this exclusive venture that caters to make your kids the 'next big thing' in terms of fashion with traditional, customized clothing. Not only clothes, the store also offers quilts, cushion covers, wall hangings that can be customized as well.

FashionStylla.com- The business of Sandeep Gaur, Fashion Stylla is an e-commerce website that offers designer jewelry, apparels and accessories from creative designers of India. The range of products provided at the website caters to all needs and that too at affordable prices.

heUpkarStore.com- The renowned brand of Upkar that commenced way back in 1972, launched its online venture delivering grocery items to Udaipurites. With a range of products including soups, cooking oil, chocolates, imported items, eatery items and more, this store is known to deliver quality products at competitive prices. However, people still prefer to walk into the Upkar store than opt online shopping.

Table 1: Details of respondents

S. No.	Tehsil	District
1	Girwa	
2	Vallabhnagar	
3	Mavli	
4	Jhadol	
5	Salumbar	
6	Sarada	Udaipur
7	Kotra	
8	Gogunda	
9	Kherwara	
10	Rishabhdeo	
11	Lasadiya	

Sources: Internet

e-Business Marketing Strategies in Udaipur District

Udaipur district is situated in the southern part of Rajasthan, which is known as 'Mewar' and Udaipur bounded on the northwest by the Aravalli range, according to the 2011 census, the total population of Udaipur city was 451,100. Including suburbs outside the city limits the population was 474,531. Udaipur is tribal district Tribal marketing strategies addresses consumers through a social context. It caters to our need as people to build and associate with consumption focused groups called 'tribes', that are emotionally connected through their similar

consumption values. Tribal Marketing strategies is the process of segmenting audiences based on shared beliefs, affinities and interests, instead of clustering by demographics such as age and gender.

e-Business Concept

What is e-Business concept and how is it essential for a successful business? It describes the basic information of the business including goals, vision, products and offers from which it will earn revenue. The effective concept is based on market analysis that will identify the customers' interests to purchase the product and how much they can pay for it.

What is e-Business concept? It is based on goals such as "Become a major bus seller or commercial enterprise" and objectives such as "have \$80 million in revenues in five years". Whether the company is prepared to achieve their goals and objectives addressed in the implementation plan for running a business and in the business plan process for startup companies.

Corporate strategies are also embedded in the e-Business concept and describe how the business concept will be implemented and can be modified in order to enhance business performance.

Business concept and market research are important to understand the market, who comprises it and what do they want. Once the market research is done, now the pricing should be established according to the competition.

Concepts of e-business in Udaipur

The city "Udaipur in Rajasthan has been selected as one of the smart cities under the ministry of urban development Gol's smart city mission. Udaipur is now required to formulate its own unique vision, mission and under 'city challenge'. E-business is the essential factor for the making smart city because smart thinking is also part of the smart city. E-business provides cost and transaction efficiency and helps business organization to enjoy economics of scale.

Factors stressing the marketing strategies for the e-business in Udaipur

E-business helps in cost reduction

E-business helps in customer satisfaction

E-business helps to acquire just-in-time information

E-business helps in transaction efficiency.

Ease of access to global market through e-business

Objectives

To assess e-business perception level by urban and rural literate consumers of Udaipur.

To enlist consumers perception level and marketing strategies to make e-business practices more consumer friendly.

To study the various factors that influence of consumers perception

Study area

The study will cover the entire district of Udaipur.

Research methodology

The study will cover the entire district of Udaipur. The study will be based on random sample of respondent consumers from both urban and rural areas. The respondents will cover all the e-business delivery hubs functioning in Udaipur city as well as selected households in urban and rural areas. Besides, the websites of main e-business companies' concept and strategies.

Having a delivery hub in Udaipur will also be visited to get detailed information on nature and type of business done by them.

Sources of Data

The study conducted with the primary, secondary and other qualitative inputs. Research has to rely hereby on the field survey techniques, *i.e.* questioners, interviews and observations as well as published and unpublished reports & records, journals, periodicals, newspapers and magazine to collect primary and secondary data. Information regarding sources is given below in detail.

Sampling technique

For the purpose of study 250 respondents were chosen. Convenience sampling has been adopted.

Tools for analysis

Percentage analysis and chart analysis

Analysis and Interpretation

Ratio of e-business consumers of Udaipur district.

A sample of 250 respondents has been taken.

Table 2: Details of respondents

Area	Population	Percentage
Urban	80	32%
Rural	80	32%
Sub-urban	50	20%
Tribal	40	16%
Total	250	100

Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section of chapter will deal with the demographic profile of respondents *i.e.* Age, Gender, Educational Qualification, Area of Residence, marital Status, Occupation, Monthly Income etc.

Opinion for the Statements that Determine the Perception towards e-Business

Respondents were asked to indicate their opinion for the statements that determine the perception towards e-Business on five point scale starting from extremely aware (5) to unaware (1)

- The score among 1.00-1.80 means **Strongly Disagree**
- The score among 1.81-2.60 means **Disagree**
- The score among 2.61-3.40 means **Neutral**
- The score among 3.41-4.20 means **Agree**
- The score among 4.21-5.00 means **Strongly Agree**

Table 3: Perception level

S. No.	Factors	Mean Score	SD	Perception
1	e-Business websites are ready and willing to help customers	4.59	0.734	Strongly Agree
2	I get better products in e-Business as compared to in-store products	4.45	0.807	Strongly Agree
3	e-Business product warranty policies are satisfactory	3.49	1.278	Agree
4	e-Business products are low priced	3.28	1.44	Neutral
5	It's easy to compare prices with e-Business	3.25	1.40	Neutral
6.	My personal information is secure	3.56	1.062	Agree
7	My privacy and security is taken care, by the seller	3.83	0.984	Agree
8	The products are packed safely	3.51	1.14	Agree
9	The products are delivered on time	3.69	1.059	Agree
10	It's time saving to purchase with e-Business	3.73	0.994	Agree

11	Websites provide customer care services	3.49	1.115	Agree
12	e-Business websites are reliable and trustworthy	3.53	1.124	Agree
13	e-Business can provide more value than traditional shopping system	3.594	1.045	Agree
14	Online shopping can create loyal customer base	4.45	0.807	Strongly Agree
15	e-Business offer great comfort while business	3.49	1.278	Agree

Source: Statistical Analysis

Satisfaction Level towards the Following Components of e-Business / e-Shopping / Online Transfer?

Satisfaction is the ultimate goal of every organization. Respondents were asked to indicate their level of satisfaction towards components of e-Business/e- shopping/online transfer five-point scale starting from highly satisfied (5) highly dissatisfied (1). To get concrete results mean is calculated for each element and in addition following criteria is used for analysis part:

- The score among 1.00-1.80 means Highly Dissatisfied
- The score among 1.81-2.60 means Dissatisfied
- The score among 2.61-3.40 means Neutral
- The score among 3.41-4.20 means Satisfied
- The score among 4.21-5.00 means Highly Satisfied

Table 4: Satisfaction level

S. No.	Factors	Mean Score	SD	Satisfaction level
1	Availability of Variety of Goods	3.83	0.984	Satisfied
2	Product Specifications	3.51	1.14	Satisfied
3	Product Pictures	3.735	0.994	Satisfied
4	Payment Options	3.59	1.045	Satisfied
5	Product Packaging	4.45	0.807	Highly Satisfied
6.	Delivery Process	3.49	1.278	Satisfied
7	Replacement Procedure	3.28	1.44	Natural
8	Money Back facility	3.25	1.40	Natural
9	Promotion Schemes	3.58	1.106	Satisfied
10	Price Comparison	3.14	1.23	Natural
11	Grievance Mechanism	3.594	1.045	Satisfied
12	Terms & Conditions	3.83	0.984	Satisfied
13	Privacy System	3.517	1.14	Satisfied
14	Website language	3.695	1.059	Satisfied

Source: Statistical Analysis

Interpretation

The table shows that, the majority of the respondents were satisfied with the given opinion. According to the table 5 Product Packaging option have is highly satisfaction level.

Table 5: Quality not up to the mark

Response	N	Percentage
Never	60	15%
Very rarely	10	2.5%
Rarely	95	23.75%
Occasionally	107	26.75%
Always	128	32%
Total	400	100.00
Mean Score	3.56	
Standard Deviation	1.062	
Result	Occasionally	

Source: Statistical Analysis

Interpretation

The above table interprets that:

- Majority of the respondents (N=128 and percentage=32%) are said always while 107 respondents said occasionally.
- Some of the respondents (N=95 and percentage= 23.75%) are said rarely
- 15% of the respondents said never while 2.5% said very rarely.
- Thus, the average score is received as 3.56 which projects that respondents said occasionally with the statement.

Findings of the study

It has been observed that out of the 250 customers of the e-Business, there are 125 male and 125 Female. In terms of age majority of the respondents (160) belongs to the age group of 21-40 years. 120 respondents belong to the age group of below 41 to 60 years. 90 respondents belong to the age group of Up to 20 years and only 30 are from the age group of above 60 years. In terms of age majority of the respondents (120) belongs to the urban area.

In the rural and urban area people are not interested to purchase health products from online. Majority of the respondents in rural area said no about the products which purchased by online and majority of the respondents said yes in urban area it clearly indicates that people in rural area are much aware e-business as compare to rural area.

Implications' and Suggestions

Web-based technologies upgrade creative conceptualization that would improve the response from technology-savvy consumers. So, the firms have to invest in such new technologies

All local products should be included in the e-Business.

One of the biggest challenges for e-Business has been the skepticism surrounding security aspects of e-commerce, which has lowered confidence levels. The only remedy to this is to strengthen the transaction security to gradually build up confidence in online payment.

Potential customers should be convinced of the benefits of shopping from home without having the pain of going out in the crowded places.

The price offered for online shopping should be made more competitive as compared to the prices of the goods available in the shops then only the customers will feel motivated to buy online.

The vendors and service providers should avoid hidden charges. This will help to avoid an increase in the price of a product.

Due to the technological development, the service providers should implement new innovative ideas to display information about the product. Now-a-day's 360-degree method is most helpful to know about all the positions of the product. This method will help to create confidence in the product. So, all the service provider's should implement these kinds of innovative methods.

Website design and quality create a positive impact on online shopping satisfaction. So, the vendor companies should concentrate more on the designing part of the websites.

Online shopping follows international market standards and does not know about the local market standard. So, the online vendors should introduce the products according to the local market standard. This will help to increase consumers' buying patterns and help the vendors to increase sales.

The respondents face major problems on the theft of credit card information, and lack of security on online payments. Implementing precautionary steps to solve these problems shall create consumer confidence in online shopping.

The reliability and responsiveness of the delivery system is the key success factor and now customers want products as their requirements and wish list, so it is suggested that they should put an option for modifying the products and services.

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